

RESULTS OF RESEARCH ON THE STUDY OF THE CONDITION OF SEEDLINGS GROWN FOREST FARM NURSERIES.

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Abstract. The article presents the results of research conducted on the study of the condition of seedlings grown in forestry nurseries. In this regard, in the studies conducted on the study of ornamental tree seeds and their planting schemes grown in forest nurseries, the seeds are very small, their size ranges from 1 mm to 20-25 mm, and the root system of seedlings, their length from 40-50 mm to 100-120 mm, was determined. Based on the obtained results, it was determined that it is necessary to develop a combined aggregate that implements the technology of preparing the land for planting and the technological process of the aggregate for the cultivation of ornamental trees and rare flower seedlings/

Key words: Forest, nursery, planting, research, result, ornamental tree, seedling, planting schemes, size, root system, rare flower seedlings, technology, technological process, aggregate, combined aggregate.

Introduction. There is a flaw in human nature that creates a problem and begins to look for ways to eliminate it. Today, maintaining a natural balance with respect to environmental protection, one of the most rugged points of the earth, stands in the main midst.

The cultivation of ornamental tree and rare flower seedlings on the land of the Forest Farm Nursery is considered productive. Therefore, special attention is paid to their cultivation. Taking into account the fact that in the studies conducted, the seeds of ornamental tree and rare flower seedlings vary in size from 1 mm to 20-25 mm, it will be necessary to pay special attention to the grinding of the soil of the lands prepared for their planting, otherwise small seeds will not be able to raise the soil layer. In addition, special attention will also need to be paid to planting seedlings grown on forestry plantation land, since planting small seedlings under such conditions will not work, the young sprouts planted will lead to drying out.

Research methods. The studies carried out determined the sizes of seedling seeds using existing methods, the lengths of the root system of seedlings prepared for cultivation in greenhouses.

Research results. Taking into account the results of the research carried out, the

requirements for the preparation of Forest Farm nurseries for planting were developed. The agrotechnical requirements for the preparation of forest nursery land for planting were formulated as follows:

- Forest Farm Nursery lands should not contain plant residues and weeds that are plowed in the fields in the spring, driven out in the fall;
- the forest farm must be plowed in the fall on the land of the nursery, ground the soil of the land plotted in the spring, open the owners of irrigation and form pushtars;
- the soil layer should be ground to a depth of 10-12 cm;
- in the processed layer, the amount of the fraction, the size of which is less than 25 mm, should not be less than 80 percent.

In accordance with the requirements for the preparation of Forest Farm nurseries for planting, great opportunities will be created to prepare the land for planting, to carry out planting work qualitatively and to collect sprouts, and to ensure the development of plants.

Research has been carried out on the study of seeds and seedlings of ornamental tree and shrubby ornamental tree grown at Andijan road greenery UK (pitomniki) and Saidulla Temirov farm in Pakhtaabad District of Andijan region specializing in forestry planting (1 and 2- photos).

1 2 3 4

a)

1-оқ қайин (лат. *Bétula*), 2-шарқ чинори (лат. *Platanus*)

3-Хинд сирени (*Индийская сирень*), 4-каталпа ([лат. Catalpa](#))

b

1 - two-paraded ginkgo (lat.*Ginkgo biloba*), 2- eldor Pine (lat. *Pinus eldarica*), 3rd guyava (lat. *Psidium*), 4th lavender (lat. *Lavandula*),

Goja 5 (lat. *Tília*)

Photos - 1. Ornamental tree, medicinal plants

Seeds (A) and seedlings (b)

In the results of the study obtained, it was found that the seeds are very small, their size varies from 1 mm to 20-25 mm (Pictures 1, a). The smaller the seeds, the more special it will be necessary to pay attention to the fractional composition of the soil of the land being prepared for them, otherwise the smaller seeds will not be able to raise the soil layer.

Research has been carried out to study the condition of seedlings grown in their greenhouses and their structure.

In the results of the resulting study, it was found that the root system of seedlings, their length varies from 40-50 mm to 100-120 mm (Figure 1, B).

The results of the study conducted found that most seedling planting schemes were adapted to the existing scheme, that is, between the rows, 60 and 90 cm (Photos 2). The results obtained were used to develop a constructive scheme of the aggregate.

a)

b)

v)

g)

d)

ye)

a) The Eastern biota, which is 5 years old (lat. Thuja orientalis); B) 2nd Annual Xind siren (lat. Lagerstroemia indica); C) Crimean Pine planted in Spring (lat. Pínus); g) magnolia planted in Spring, Grandiflora (lat. Magnolia Grandiflora); d) 4th Annual Virgin arch, (lat. Juníperus); e) 1st Annual Shamshot, Samshut (lat. Búxus
2-picture. Ornamental trees and rare flower seedlings grown in forestry nurseries

In modern times, existing aggregates or adapted variants have been used for the lack of development of special aggregates that prepare land for planting for the cultivation of ornamental tree and rare flower seedlings on Forest Farm Nursery land. This in turn leads to excessive energy consumption as well as increased operating costs. The increase in the number of accesses of aggregates to the field, on the other hand, leads to a violation of the

structure of the soil.

The research carried out assumes the development of a combined aggregate, which carries out the technology and technological processes of preparing land for planting for the cultivation of ornamental tree and rare flower seedlings on Forest Farm Nursery lands in one transition of the aggregate.

Conclusion.1. In accordance with the requirements for the preparation of Forest Farm nurseries for planting, great opportunities will be created to prepare the land for planting, to carry out planting work qualitatively and to collect sprouts, and to ensure the development of plants.

2. In studies of ornamental tree seeds, seedlings grown in forest nurseries and schemes for planting them, it was found that seeds are very small, their size varies from 1 mm to 20-25 mm, and the root system of seedlings, their length varies from 40-50 mm to 100-120 mm.

3. The results obtained determined that for the cultivation of ornamental tree and rare flower seedlings, it is necessary to develop a combined aggregate, which carries out the technology and technological processes of preparing land for planting in one transition of the aggregate.

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